

Factors Affecting the Consumer Satisfaction with the Role of Social Media Influencers in Ready to Wear Clothing Brands

Malik Muhammad Faisal¹, Manzoom Akhtar², Zia ur Rehman³, Muhammad Hafeez⁴, Kashif Mehmood⁵

Abstract

Social media influencers, as opposed to celebrities or public figures who are well-known through traditional media, are "ordinary individuals" who have become "online celebrities" through creating and posting content on social media. They frequently have some understanding of specific topics, including lifestyle, healthy living, travel, food, and fashion. This study attempts to provide "a clearer understanding of what drives the effectiveness of influencer marketing" in terms of their capacity to affect consumer brand attitudes, in accordance with past research. To accomplish the aforementioned, this study experimentally assesses a conceptual model examining how SMI power can influence consumer perceptions of the marketed brands. This research study is quantitative. For this study, researcher gathered the data from the populations of two twin cities Rawalpindi and Islamabad. As of 2022, the current population of Rawalpindi and Islamabad is 2,327,000 and 1,198,000. The main focus of this study is on the individuals who are directly or indirectly involve in the purchase of ready-to-wear clothes recommended by Social Media Influencers to see how Social Media Influencers (SMI) affect the brand experience of customer. Researchers collected the data by using the survey method through personal visits to respondents and used a Convenience sampling because in convenience sampling samples are easy to collect. Before collecting data, it enables to refine your questionnaire through reliability of instrument. Cronbach's alpha is used in the present study. Based on research results, Social Media Influencers have a greater effect on the perceived satisfaction of customers in the purchase of ready-to-wear clothing. Managers of Ready-to-wear clothing brands should pay attention to improving their expertise and authenticity especially if they intend to establish their business in ready-to-wear clothing. This research implies that SMIs performing high levels of expertise and authenticity are considered to have high perceived satisfaction. Comparatively, those with a low level of expertise and authenticity are considered to have low perceived satisfaction.

Key Words: Consumer Satisfaction, Social Media Influencers, Perceived trustworthiness, Perceived SMI, Communication Skills, Perceived SMI satisfaction

1. Introduction

A social media influencer has hundreds of thousands or millions of followers. In addition to sharing their daily lives with customers and interacting with a great variety of media assets (films, photographs, audio, etc.), influencers can also add to customer feedback and comments on online social networks. Because of their knowledge with and following on social networks, they have a lot of influence. In the context of digital media, influencers have a tremendous impact on consumer decision-making and purchasing behaviour. The best illustration of the influence of influencers is the American teen icon Kylie Jenner, a teen influencer with 100 million Instagram followers and 25 million Twitter followers. Many companies have used social media influencers as part of their marketing plans in recent years to boost customer empathy and promote consumer engagement. Millennials, the first generation to exclusively use digital technology, like to communicate via mobile SMS and SNS channels, and the use of social media influencers as a marketing tactic has increased substantially. With the expansion of social media, the concept of "influencers" has become a modern phenomenon. A person who interacts with a sizable, unfamiliar audience is an influencer. This audience's direct acquisition as opposed to institutional intermediaries like the entertainment or sports sectors. Millions of people follow the most popular influencers on social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram, making them comparable to well-known athletes or celebrities from the entertainment or sports industries (Gräve, 2017). Consumer choices are impacted by By social media influencers or their friends, who may advise them and talk about the newest fashion trends in the area, especially for young consumers. The most efficient way to reach the largest possible audience and increase corporate profitability, Mangold & Faulds (2009) is through a social media platform like Instagram or Facebook that provides details and information about the products and services. Historically, Instagram has been used mostly for posting eye-catching photographs and comments. But social media platforms like Instagram have evolved into a venue that companies use to promote and market their wares. This is done to bring the viewers' attention to the images rather than the words (Hanson, 2018).

Because of the useful and original content posted on social media platforms, they have attracted consumers' attention to their lifestyle, attitude, and personal traits displayed in influencers' profiles on websites like blogs, YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram. Instagram users are encouraged to follow social media influencers by "power middle

¹ Assistant Professor, Faculty of Management and Economics, Ghazi University Dera Ghazi Khan, Pakistan, mmfaisal@gudgk.edu.my

² Assistant Professor, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan, manzom92@hotmail.com

³ Assistant Professor, University Institute of Management Sciences, PMAS-Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, zia.rehman@uaar.edu.pk

influences" who have a following of between 100,000 and 200,000 thanks to their success (Chen, 2016). A social media influencer's growth in popularity is shown by an increase in followers.

1.1. Background of the Study

Purchase intention is defined as a person's conscious decision to buy a particular Brand and a plan to purchase particular items or services (Spears & Singh, 2004). Goyal (2014) A person's decision to buy things will be influenced by the effects of marketing aspects (Hausman & Siekpe, 2009). Consumers will analyse the information after compiling their prior experience, preferences, and referrals from others. Customers will then assess their options before choosing whether or not to make a purchase (Chi et al., 2011). Purchase intention is used to study customer behaviour as it serves as a predictor of actual purchases (Kim et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2015; Pavlou, 2003). Lisichkova & Othman (2017) assert that a consumer's real purchasing intention is significantly influenced by their intention to buy.

For increasing sales of goods and services and generating profits, businesses now recognise how crucial consumer intent is (Hosein, 2012). Rebelo (2017) asserts that it is crucial to examine how consumers view SMI's trustworthiness when SMI trustworthiness will affect consumers' purchase intentions and the advertisers' main objective is to influence consumers to form purchase intentions to buy the Products that are promoted by marketing influencers. In the virtual world of social media, for instance, honesty has evolved as a crucial personality quality of a SMI.

In a straightforward setting, we can define satisfaction as an indicator of how well a company's goods and services live up to client expectations. However, the focus of our study is on how social media influencers affect and please the customers of ready-to-wear clothing brands. After reviewing the literature, the writers have determined the six most crucial aspects that can affect perceived satisfaction. In this study, we will examine how social media influencers' perceived satisfaction with Ready-to-Wear clothing brands are influenced by their credibility, knowledge, communication skills, influence, and authenticity.

To investigate how perceived Satisfaction with the role of Social Media influencers in ready-to-wear clothing brands is affected by factors including trustworthiness, expertise, influence, authenticity, and communication skills.

1.2. Significance of the Study

Hootsuite estimates that by 2020, the platform has over 112.5 million active users (up 5.4% from 2019), and that number will expand to at least 117.2 million in 2021 in only the United States (Hootsuite, 2019). Therefore, it should not be surprising that influencers on social media have become increasingly well-liked. Social media influencers (SMI) are third-party proponents who attempt to influence consumers' opinions of a brand (Freberg et al., 2011).

1.3 Scope of the Study

This study's goal is to establish the difference between the dependent and independent factors. The dependent variables in this study are influence, communication skills, trustworthiness, knowledge, and authenticity. These social media influencer variables in the context of ready-to-wear clothing brands have never been studied before.

1.4 Structure of the Study

In the 2nd section of the study, literature review is written and after that methodology is explained. After this data was analysed and results discussed according to the hypothesis. Then study concluded and submitted suggestions.

2. Literature Review

The study is based on two interconnected theories. It includes the "theory of consumer socialization" (Moschis & Churchill, 1978), and the "theory of market signaling" are all included (Spence, 1973). These have been put up as explanations for how Social Media Influencer power affects consumer perceptions of the brand. The influence of SMI power on customer brand perceptions is defined as "the influencer's ability to raise the probability that a consumer will buy a product that has received their support". The theoretical literature is reviewed and these theories are discussed in detail in the following subsections concerning marketing. (Nafees et al., 2021).

2.1. Consumer Socialization Theory

According to the notion of consumer socialization, a SMI can be viewed as a medium of communication that reaches customers and spreads values, opinions, motives, and actions. Moschis & Churchill (1978) As a result, through three connected processes—"modeling, reinforcement, and social interaction"—consumers learn from the socialization agent the concepts and actions that they later apply to their own lives. A SMI is supposed to function as an agent of computer-mediated socialisation. Therefore, customers that adhere to a SMI are more likely to take on its values, opinions, motives, and behaviours. As they learn more about the product and how to use it from the SMI, customers frequently adopt the SMI's behaviour and attitude and are encouraged to act in ways associated with the SMI being followed. Customers are urged to perform in ways that are consistent with the SMI they are following and commonly adopt the SMI's actions and attitudes. (Nafees et al., 2021).

2.2. Market Signaling Theory

The first discussion of signalling theory was made by (Spence, 1973). When there is inadequate information sharing between sender and receiver, such as when buyers and sellers have different levels of product expertise, the theory is relevant. While purchasers have a relative less knowledge. During the experience or credence goods purchasing process, information asymmetry is likely involved. For instance, buyers of experience goods find it challenging to

evaluate a product's quality at deciding before making a buy. Venues, theatres, and cafés are a few examples. The reputation and trustworthiness of the signaler contribute significantly to establishing the success of a marketing signal (Herbig & Milewicz, 1996). The impact of the marketing signal is increased by a signaler who is credible and reputable. Herbig and Milewicz (1996) claim that a Buyers may perceive the promoted goods as being of higher quality if the signaler has a decent image (Nafees et al., 2021).

2.3. Defining Social Media Influencers

Influencers on social media can influence public opinion and serve in marketing for businesses (Freberg et al., 2011). SMIs have the potential to influence the audience in favour of the company being advertised. Liu et al., (2012) Social media influencers are those who have self-cultivated a large audience on social media by successful self-presentation. The concept of social media influencers is not new and dates back to the mid-2000s during the blogosphere era (Borchers, 2019). Additionally, influencer marketing helps in business development because SMIs are constantly viewed as role models and have an impact on their audience, claim (Sudha and Sheena, 2017).

2.4. Perceived SMI Trustworthiness

As stated, "the level of trust in the communicator's intent to convey the statements as most genuine" is how they defined trustworthiness. Trustworthiness had a greater influence than expertise (McGinnies and Ward 1980). Based on previous research, this finding implies that perceptions of SMI trustworthiness will buffer the relationship between SMI power and customer attitudes toward the brand. This connection may be explained by the rise in SMI strength that results from sustained viewers interaction, which inspires customers' faith in the SMI's dependability. The audience in this process will probably presume the SMI's dependability to the brand they are supporting, representing the SMI's positive feelings about the product. (Nafees et al., 2021)

The words "the ratifier's believability, honesty, and integrity" characterise trustworthiness. Trustworthiness is a component of source credibility, and influencers must possess it in order to sway their audience Kim et al., (2018). If customers trust SMI's suggested products, they are more likely to buy them (Liu et al., 2015). Rebelo's (2017) research, the trustworthy influencer was more compelling.

2.5. Perceived SMI Satisfaction

The authenticity and quality of the information that SMI shares have a strong influence on the impact of SMI, as has been identified (Magno & Cassia, 2018; Hollowell et al., 2019; Popescu & Ciurlău, 2019). The influence of perceived relevance on consumers' responses to advertising has usually been examined in new media contexts such as online and mobile ads. The same pattern of results has been found. In online context, personal relevance generates a favorable attitude toward the repetitive online ad, the product and the website that the ad is implemented in (Campbell & Wright, 2008).

2.6 Perceived SMI Communication Skills

Influencers are important for oral communication channels in a digital context. As a result, effective communication skills are a crucial requirement for influencers who want to engage with customers. It is more than just that you communicate well; it also implies that you share knowledge and information with customers and express your views and feelings in a way that they can trust. Influencers' communication abilities are becoming increasingly crucial in especially because they have recently advertised and sold things via live video broadcasting. Because real-time communication between consumers and influencers offers the greatest benefits, this commerce is taking place now. Therefore, in order to convince today's customer are exposed to a range of communications and are sceptical of the disclosure of personal information—influencers must communicate with them through their communication abilities. That is, it is crucial to grasp what customers actually want through interaction and to empathise with them through interaction rather than pressuring them to listen to information they do not want (Ryu & Han, 2021).

2.6. Perceived SMI Influence

The influence of influencers is not evaluated according to any particular standard. As a result, it is challenging to evaluate an influencer's influence or impact based solely on their followers or other actions. However, with SNS, influencer content may quickly reach and spread to possibly millions of people. Therefore, consumers' attitudes and actions are impacted by an Sponsor's Justification, suggestions, or unfavorable judgements of a specific goods or brand. According to this view, influencers who can evoke empathy, familiarity, and credibility can exert more of an influence than conventional mass media. This is another reason why many businesses incorporate influencer marketing into their marketing plans. Influencers' influence is particularly expanding as the marketing environment changes quickly, threatening to current online shopping malls, and it is considered that influencers' influence will continue to grow as they become new distribution channels. (Ryu & Han, 2021).

2.7. Perceived SMI Authenticity

Authenticity has recently taken centre stage across a large range of industries (e.g., social science, marketing, etc). It is difficult to define authenticity because so many aspects, including moral behavior, Perception, internal processes, and interpersonal or social situations influence it.

2.8. The authenticity of Social Media Influencers

Balancing an authentic voice with brand promotion methods is important for a SMI's success (Balaban & Mustăţea, 2019). Audrezet et al., (2020) have developed a four-path paradigm to conceptualise how influencers might manage

authenticity while exploring SMIs as brand endorsers. They discovered that SMIs intentionally employ two methods to control the conflicts they experience when interacting with business possibilities. The strategies of passionate authenticity and transparent authenticity. When producing interesting and purely enjoyable digital content, SMIs apply the passionate authenticity strategy. On the other hand, they use the transparent authenticity technique when they are delivering fact based knowledge on a good or service (Audrezet et al., 2020). Transparent authenticity can also take the shape of publishing uncut material or revealing knowledge about a collaboration among the Influencer and a brand. Porous authenticity is a word Abidin (2018) used to explain the outcomes of publishing unedited content. By giving them the information they seek, influencers encourage direct consumer participation. Consumers trust and rely on the knowledge and opinions offered by SMI who communicate with them on the network, and they do not reject or have a negative perception of it. Knowledge is interpreted as if friends told you about it personally, and influencers' Experiences from actual life are considered to be genuine material. Customers subscribe to influencer content at all because influencers are more real than celebrities. Bloggers seem to be actually using the products and brands they advertise, and they appear to be giving consumers their genuine analyses and thoughts. Customers relate to influencers as a consequence, view them as reliable, and believe that their acts are real. Recently, well-known TikTok influencers posted a "anti-Trump" video without any sponsored commercials.

2.9. The Authenticity Model of (Mass-Oriented) Computer-Mediated Communication and its Relevance for Social Media Influencers

Lee (2020) has proposed an integrative theoretical approach to study computer-mediated communication that uses authenticity as its central unifying element. Lee defined three subcomponents: authenticity of the provider, authenticity of the content, and authenticity of engagement. Whether a communicator is truly who they say they are is a question that is addressed by authenticity of source. The individual who (allegedly) created a message is represented by the authenticity of the source in this framework. According to Lee, an observer's expectations are framed by stereotypes about social categories when a communication source is unknown. Furthermore, the credibility, reliability, and expertise of the source are related to its authenticity. As a result, the source credibility of SMIs is connected to this sub-component of authenticity. A message is truthfully representing its object is measured by the authenticity of message, which is the second subcomponent in Lee's (2020) model. This object may be a person, including the source, an occasion, or a problem. The issue of whether or not an interaction is real is at the centre of the third subcomponent

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

of authenticity in Lee's (2020) model. It also considers how closely individuals believe they are engaging in a real interaction. The perceived authenticity of connection can be boosted via reciprocity and spontaneity. The three subcomponents that pertain to authenticity listed above are linked and dependent on one another, and they can heighten the perceived level of authenticity.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

A research design is a plan, structure, or investigational approach that is conceptualized to achieve the answer to research questions or problems. In a simple context, we can define satisfaction as a measure of how well a company's products and services meet the expectations of customers. But our study focuses on the perceived satisfaction of customers with the role of Social Media Influencers (SMI) in ready-to-wear clothing brands. We analyzed how Social Media Influencers influence and satisfy the consumers of ready-to-wear clothing brands. For this purpose, the

author reviewed the literature and determined the five most crucial factors that affect the perceived satisfaction of consumers with the role of Social Media Influencers (SMI). These crucial factors are trustworthiness, expertise, communication skills, influence, and authenticity. In our research, we will investigate the effect of these factors on the perceived satisfaction of customers with the role of Social Media Influencers (SMI).

This research study is quantitative. Quantitative research is a deductive and objective approach to solve problems in Positivism Theory. Research can be based on several theories such as Positivism, Realism, Interpretivism, and Pragmatism. It includes experimentation, survey, case study, etc. But we conducted our research by using the survey method. A survey is a research method used to gather data from a predetermined group of respondents to study and gain information.

3.2. Population Study

The population can be defined as a group of individuals or objects which the researcher tends to study or investigate. We chose Generation Y and Z as our target population. Generation Y are Millennials who born between 1980 and 1994. While, Generation Z includes digital Natives who born between 1995 and 2010. This is the reason, we targeted these two generations for our research.

According to the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, the current estimated population of Pakistan is 229,230,939. For this study, researcher gathered the data from the populations of two twin cities Rawalpindi and Islamabad. As of 2022, the current population of Rawalpindi and Islamabad is 2,327,000 and 1,198,000. The main focus of our study is on the individuals who are directly or indirectly involve in the purchase of ready-to-wear clothes recommended by Social Media Influencers to see how Social Media Influencers (SMI) affect the brand experience of customer. We collected the data by using the survey method through personal visits to respondents.

3.3. Sampling Techniques

A sample can be defined as a group of individuals or objects which is drawn from a larger population for study or investigation. While sampling refers to the method used to choose a sample from entire population. There are two types of sampling techniques Probability and Non-probability. In Probability sampling, a researcher uses a tool based on probability theory to draw a sample from a larger population. A person must be chosen randomly in probability sampling.

Non-probability sampling is defined as a sampling technique in which the selection of a sample is based on the researcher's subjective judgment. As compared to probability sampling, in non-probability sampling every member of the target population has an equal possibility of being chosen. In our study, we chose non-probability sampling. This is so because non-probability sampling is a comparatively simple technique and the results are largely dependent on the researcher's expertise. We used a Convenience sampling because because in convenience sampling samples are easy to collect.

In research, it is very crucial to test the sample that will represent the entire target population. But, in some conditions where the population is way too large then the researcher might not be able to conduct a test for the entire population. This is the reason why researchers emphasize convenience sampling. Non-probability sampling technique is also a cost-efficient and time-saving method.

3.4. Sample Size

The sample size is determined by the size of the population. A larger sample size is typically expected to generate more accurate results. Different researchers have different perspectives regarding the accuracy of the sample size. 400 to 600 respondents is the estimated sample size to generate reliable and accurate results from the collected data. The acceptable sample size is a minimum 30 and maximum 500 respondents (Hossain, 2011). Based on several studies, the ideal sample size is 200 to 500 respondents for conducting multiple regressions and covariance analysis.

For our study, we took a sample size of 200 respondents, and the data of respondents is analyzed by using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software. SPSS tool is used to test the reliability and accuracy of data.

3.5. Instrument of Data Collection

Data on the perceived satisfaction of customers and other independent variables with the role of SMI was gathered by conducting a survey. There were three sections of the questionnaire. The respondent must complete section A of the survey, which requests demographic information including age, gender, education level, etc. While section B includes details about the Social Media Influencer (SMI) that the respondent trust and follows. In section C, questions about the independent and dependent variables were asked. The survey consisted of closed-ended questions measured on a 5-point Likert scale. Respondents were given a choice of five options, numbered from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates strongly disagree, 2 indicates disagree, 3 indicates Neutral, 4 indicates agree, and 5 indicates strongly agree.

3.6. Data Collection Process

Data on the perceived satisfaction of customers and other independent variables with the role of SMI was gathered by conducting a survey. A questionnaire was distributed in a hard form to the individuals that lie under the generation Y and Z. Additionally, we created a Google questionnaire and sent the link to several social media users that lie under the generation Y and Z through whatsapp so they could respond to the survey at any time and anywhere they want. For data analysis, SPSS software is used. Before collecting data, it enable to refine your questionnaire through

reliability of instrument. Cronbach's alpha is used in the present study. The value of Cronbach's is acceptable if value is near to 1 and less than 0.50 is not acceptable

3.7. Data Analysis Techniques

We used SPSS software (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) to analyze the data. Structural equation model (SEM) is method of survey-based research which is used for the optimization of variance of dependent variable. The most recent method we used is based on factor analysis and multiple regressions. We used Multiple regression because it seems appropriate for the current study.

4. Analysis and Findings

This chapter covers all the results of the study with the help of tables. Data on the perceived satisfaction of customers and other independent variables with the role of SMI was gathered by conducting a survey. A questionnaire was distributed in a hard form to the individuals that lie under the generation Y and Z. Additionally, we created a Google questionnaire and sent the link to several social media users that lie under the generation Y and Z so they could respond to the survey at any time and anywhere they want. For our research, we gathered the data from the populations of two twin cities Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Almost 200 questionnaires were distributed out of which 100 were filled through personal visits to respondents and the rest 100 questionnaires were filled through a Google questionnaire link which was shared on WhatsApp groups. Out of 200 questionnaires, 177 were complete and 23 were incomplete which we excluded, For data analysis, SPSS software is used.

Considering the research objectives results are presented accordingly. To discover and analyze the relationship of variables different statistical techniques have been applied. Results are summarized as follows:

4.1. Results and Discussions

In the current study, we have investigated the effect of trustworthiness, expertise, communication skills, influence, and authenticity on the perceived satisfaction of customers with the role of SMI in ready-to-wear clothing brands. To analyze the demographic characteristics of the respondent, a frequency distribution test have been applied.

4.2. Data Analysis

Following are some tests that are applied on data:

4.2.1. Descriptive Data Analysis

Descriptive analysis is used to analyze and explain the main characteristics of collected data in quantitative form. All items of dependent and independent variables are measured on a 5-point Likert scale. To increase the visibility, results are presented in tables:

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Serial no.	Variables name	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Trustworthiness	9	0.856
2	Expertise	9	0.900
3	Communication skills	8	0.866
4	Influence	10	0.914
5	Authenticity	7	0.926
6	Satisfaction	4	0.799

In the current study, we used Cronbach's alpha as a reliability statistics. Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the internal consistency and reliability of scales used in the instrument. Mainly, it is used to measure the reliability of a scale. The value of Cronbach's alpha is acceptable if it is near to 1. If the value of Cronbach's alpha is less than 0.70 then it will be unacceptable.

The above table shows the reliability of all independent variables i.e. trustworthiness, expertise, communication skills, influence, authenticity, and dependent variable i.e. Satisfaction. The value of Cronbach's alpha for all variables including dependent and independent is greater than 0.70 which means all scales are reliable.

4.2.2. Inferential Statistics

The regression results in table show the impact of trustworthiness, expertise, communication skills, influence, and authenticity on the perceived satisfaction of customers with the role of Social Media Influencers in ready-to-wear clothing brands.

Table 2 shows that all independent variables are significant except authenticity. It also shows the beta coefficient value of expertise is negative. It means out of 5 hypotheses 3 have been approved and the other 2 are rejected. The criteria for the hypothesis to be accepted is that the significance level must be less than 0.05 and the t-value should be above 1.96.

Table 2: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Relationship	Beta Coefficient	t-values	Hypothesis Accepted
H1	Trustworthiness → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	0.519***	5.509	Yes
H2	Expertise → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	-0.211*	-2.005	No
H3	Communication skills → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	0.319**	2.593	Yes
H4	Influence → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	0.361**	2.873	Yes
H5	Authenticity → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	0.006	0.69	No

$R^2 = 0.491$, $F = 32.945$ ***, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.0005$

49.1% variation in perceived satisfaction of customers with the role of Social Media Influencers in ready-to-wear clothing brands is caused by trustworthiness, expertise, communication skills, influence, and authenticity while the rest of 59.1% variation is caused by other variables which have not been explained by the current model.

Table 3

Hypothesis	Relationship	Beta Coefficient	t-values	Hypothesis Accepted
H1	Trustworthiness → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	0.447***	5.140	Yes
H2	Communication Skills → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	0.273*	2.307	Yes
H3	Influence → Satisfaction with the role of SMI	0.274**	2.599	Yes

$R^2 = 0.479$, $F = 52.947$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.0005$

Table 4

Hypothesis	Relationship	Beta Coefficient	t-values	Hypothesis Accepted
H1	Expertise → SWSIM	0.390***	4.295	Yes
H2	Authenticity → SWSIM	0.244**	3.075	Yes

$R^2 = 0.276$, $f = 33.180$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.0005$

There is a moderate correlation between Authenticity and Influence as well as between expertise and communication skills. The error has occurred due to this strong correlation between independent variables. Therefore, we removed expertise and authenticity from our model because these two scales are overlapping with the scales of communication skills and influence due to high similarities between them. As a result, the distance between R^2 and Adjusted R^2 decreased and the value of f improved. The significant value of F shows that the current model significantly predict the dependent variable.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

5.1. Practical Implications

Based on research results, Social Media Influencers have a greater effect on the perceived satisfaction of customers in the purchase of ready-to-wear clothing. Managers of Ready-to-wear clothing brands should pay attention to improving their expertise and authenticity especially if they intend to establish their business in ready-to-wear clothing. This research implies that SMIs performing high levels of expertise and authenticity are considered to have high perceived satisfaction. Comparatively, those with a low level of expertise and authenticity are considered to have low perceived satisfaction. Expertise and Authenticity of Social Media Influencers also influence the purchase intention of customers to a greater extent. Therefore, management needs to pay special attention to these two variables. Furthermore, the trustworthiness, Communication skills, and Influence of SMI also demand equal attention in satisfying the consumers of ready-to-wear clothing brands. Followers mostly prefer SMI who is trustworthy, an expert in his or her skills, and communicate more often with their followers to keep them up-to-date with the latest information about ready-to-wear clothing brands. It can be also really helpful for managers in improving their image. SMIs must keep themselves relevant by consistently working on their expertise, trustworthiness, authenticity, communication skills, and influence.

5.2. Theoretical Implications

For the first time, perceived satisfaction from the perspective of clothing brands has been researched. Our research focuses on how social media influencers influence and please the users of ready-to-wear clothing manufacturers. The researcher identified the six most important factors that can influence perceived pleasure after reviewing the articles. In the present study, we looked at how social media Influencers affect consumers' perceptions of brand satisfaction for ready-to-wear garments. We have looked at how factors like credibility, knowledge, influence, and authenticity affect how well customers perceive the role of SMI. This study looked at connections with social networking sites, which have become the main channel for Influencer marketing. One of the earliest studies to examine these linkages in social media is this one. Furthermore, only brands of ready-to-wear clothes were included in this investigation. Whether knowledge and authenticity are relevant when evaluated independently or not, the effect of perceived satisfaction with trustworthiness, influence, and communication abilities is considerable.

5.3. Suggestions for Future Research

This study looked at interactions regarding social networking sites, which have become the main channel for influencer marketing. This study is among the first to examine these connections within social media networks. Additionally, only brands of ready-to-wear clothes were included in this investigation. Other significant aspects weren't included in the new proposal. Future studies should take into account additional variables (additional dependent, independent, moderating, or mediating variables) that could affect the choice of ready-to-wear clothing labels. Additionally, we can research the relationship between future satisfaction and other factors like attractiveness, goodwill, credibility, etc. We gathered information from the twin cities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad, but in the future, other researchers could be able to gather information from other Pakistani cities. Although there are different sample methods available, we chose convenience sampling for the data collection in this study. Although our sample size was limited (around 177 samples), we can collect vast amounts of data in the future. Consumers will consider an Influencer's reputation more since businesses are more concerned with social value and sustainability in a time when relationships are seen as vital. From this vantage point, we anticipate that the findings of this study will further academic and applied research on Influencer marketing communications.

5.4. Limitations

This research has several limitations. First, there is a lack of experience. We are not expert researchers but we have tried our best to cover all the aspects relating to this research. We didn't have much time to thoroughly study the previous work of researchers relating to. The sample size we draw from the entire population of Rawalpindi and Islamabad is comparatively very small because the estimated population of Rawalpindi and Islamabad is 2,327,000 and 1,198,000 and the sample size we took is 200. The sampling technique we used is Convenience sampling which is a non-probability sampling technique. In non-probability sampling, every member of the target population has an equal possibility of being chosen. Non-probability sampling has some drawbacks, including the difficulty to generalize survey results to the population, there is a possibility of under- or over-representation of the population, and inaccurate results because of the reasons why some individuals decided to participate and others do not. If we had time we would have chosen random sampling because, in random sampling, it is comparatively easy to generalize survey results. It is a simpler sampling technique and there are fewer chances of biased results.

References

- Abdullah, T., Deraman, S. N. S., Zainuddin, S. A., Azmi, N. F., Abdullah, S. S., Anuar, N. I. M., ... & Hasan, H. (2020). Impact of Social Media Influencer on Instagram User Purchase Intention towards the Fashion Products: The Perspectives of UMK Pengkalan Chepa Campus Students. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine* 7(8), 2589-2598.
- Abidin, C. (2016). Visibility labour: Engaging with Influencers' fashion brands and# OOTD advertorial campaigns on Instagram. *Media International Australia*, 161(1), 86-100.
- Ahmed, Z., Asim, M., & Saleem, M. F. (2019). Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Buying Behavior: The Mediating Effect of Word of Mouth (WOM). A Survey of Retail Markets of Karachi. *Journal of Business Administration and Management Sciences (JOBAMS)*, 3(1), 39-47.
- AlFarraj, O., Alalwan, A. A., Obeidat, Z. M., Baabdullah, A., Aldmour, R., & Al-Haddad, S. (2021). Examining the impact of influencers' credibility dimensions: attractiveness, trustworthiness and expertise on the purchase intention in the aesthetic dermatology industry. *Review of International Business and Strategy*, 31(3), 355-374.
- Audrezet, A., de Kerviler, G., & Moulard, J. G. (2020). Authenticity under threat: When social media influencers need to go beyond self-presentation. *Journal of business research*, 117, 557-569.
- Balaban, D. C., & Szambolics, J. (2022). A Proposed Model of Self-Perceived Authenticity of Social Media Influencers. *Media and Communication*, 10(1), 235-246.
- Bigne, E., Andreu, L., Perez, C., & Ruiz, C. (2020). Brand love is all around: loyalty behaviour, active and passive social media users. *Current issues in tourism*, 23(13), 1613-1630.

- Campbell, D. E., & Wright, R. T. (2008). Shut-Up I Don't Care: Understanding The Role Of Relevance and Interactivity on Customer Attitudes Toward Repetitive Online Advertising. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 9(1), 62-76.
- Chen, Y. (2016). The rise of 'micro-influencers' on Instagram. *Journal of Digital and Social Marketing*, 7, 105-121.
- Chi, H., Yeh, H. R., & Tsai, Y. C. (2011). The Influences Of Perceived Value On Consumer Purchase Intention: The Moderating Effect Of Advertising Endorser. *Journal of International Management Studies*, 6(1), 1-6.
- Chua, T. H. H., & Chang, L. (2016). Follow me and like my beautiful selfies: Singapore teenage girls' engagement in self-presentation and peer comparison on social media. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 55, 190-197.
- Forbes, K. (2016). Examining the beauty industry's use of social influencers. *Elon Journal of Undergraduate Research in Communications*, 7(2), 78-87.
- Freberg, K., Graham, K., McGaughey, K., & Freberg, L. A. (2011). Who are the social media influencers? A study of public perceptions of personality. *Public relations review*, 37(1), 90-92.
- Gibson, N. (2018). *An Analysis of the Impact of Social Media Marketing on Individuals' Attitudes and Perceptions at NOVA Community College*, OTS Master's Level Projects & Papers. 588.
- Grafström, J., Jakobsson, L., & Wiede, P. (2018). *The Impact of Influencer Marketing on Consumers' Attitudes: A Qualitative Study on What Reasons Affect Millennials' Attitudes by Influencer Marketing in Sweden*. Independent thesis Basic level (degree of Bachelor): Jönköping Universty.
- Gräve, J. F. (2017, July). Exploring the perception of influencers vs. traditional celebrities: are social media stars a new type of endorser?. In *Proceedings of the 8th international conference on Social Media & Society* (pp. 1-5).
- Hanson, L. (2018). The fashion brand's guide to creating excellent visual content. Retrieved from which PLM. <https://www.whichplm.com/the-fashion-brandsguide-to-creating-excellent-visual-content>.
- Hausman, A. V., & Siekpe, J. S. (2009). The effect of web interface features on consumer online purchase intentions. *Journal of business research*, 62(1), 5-13.
- Herbig, P., & Milewicz, J. (1996). Market signaling: A review. *Management Decision: Quarterly Review of Management Technology*, 34(1), 35-45.
- Hosein, N. Z. (2012). Measuring the purchase intention of visitors to the auto show. *Journal of Management & Marketing Research*, 9(1), 1-17.
- Husnain, M., & Toor, A. (2017). The impact of social network marketing on consumer purchase intention in Pakistan: Consumer engagement as a mediator. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 10(1), 167-199.
- Jarrar, Y., Awobamise, A. O., & Aderibigbe, A. A. (2020). Effectiveness of influencer marketing vs social media sponsored advertising. *Utopía y praxis latinoamericana: revista internacional de filosofía iberoamericana y teoría social*, (12), 40-54.
- Kim, J., & Forsythe, S. (2008). Adoption of virtual try-on technology for online apparel shopping. *Journal of interactive marketing*, 22(2), 45-59.
- Lee, J. A., & Eastin, M. S. (2020). I like what she's# endorsing: The impact of female social media influencers' perceived sincerity, consumer envy, and product type. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 20(1), 76-91.
- Lin, C. A., Crowe, J., Pierre, L., & Lee, Y. (2021). Effects of parasocial interaction with an instafamous influencer on brand attitudes and purchase intentions. *The Journal of Social Media in Society*, 10(1), 55-78.
- Lisichkova, N., & Othman, Z. (2017). The Impact of Influencers on Online Purchase Intent.(May 2017), 1-64.
- Liu, C. L. E., Sinkovics, R. R., Pezderka, N., & Haghirian, P. (2012). Determinants of consumer perceptions toward mobile advertising—a comparison between Japan and Austria. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 26(1), 21-32.
- Liu, S., Jiang, C., Lin, Z., Ding, Y., Duan, R., & Xu, Z. (2015). Identifying effective influencers based on trust for electronic word-of-mouth marketing: A domain-aware approach. *Information sciences*, 306, 34-52.
- Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer marketing: how message value and credibility affect consumer trust of branded content on social media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 58-73.
- Magno, F., & Cassia, F. (2018). The impact of social media influencers in tourism. *Anatolia*, 29(2), 288-290.
- Mangold, W. G., & Faulds, D. J. (2009). Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix. *Business horizons*, 52(4), 357-365.
- McGinnies, E., & Ward, C. D. (1980). Better liked than right: Trustworthiness and expertise as factors in credibility. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 6(3), 467-472.
- Moschis, G. P., & Churchill Jr, G. A. (1978). Consumer socialization: A theoretical and empirical analysis. *Journal of marketing research*, 15(4), 599-609.
- Nafees, L., Cook, C. M., Nikolov, A. N., & Stoddard, J. E. (2021). Can social media influencer (SMI) power influence consumer brand attitudes? The mediating role of perceived SMI credibility. *Digital Business*, 1(2), 100008.
- Pop, R. A., Săplăcan, Z., Dabija, D. C., & Alt, M. A. (2022). The impact of social media influencers on travel decisions: The role of trust in consumer decision journey. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(5), 823-843.
- Pop, R. A., Săplăcan, Z., Dabija, D. C., & Alt, M. A. (2022). The impact of social media influencers on travel decisions: The role of trust in consumer decision journey. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(5), 823-843.

- Rebelo, M. F. (2017). *How influencers' credibility on Instagram is perceived by consumers and its impact on purchase intention* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Ryu, E. A., & Han, E. (2021). Social media influencer's reputation: Developing and validating a multidimensional scale. *Sustainability*, 13(2), 631.
- Smith, L. G., Gillespie, N., Callan, V. J., Fitzsimmons, T. W., & Paulsen, N. (2017). Injunctive and descriptive logics during newcomer socialization: The impact on organizational identification, trustworthiness, and self-efficacy. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 38(4), 487-511.
- Spears, N., & Singh, S. N. (2004). Measuring attitude toward the brand and purchase intentions. *Journal of current issues & research in advertising*, 26(2), 53-66.
- Spence, M. (1978). Job market signaling. In *Uncertainty in economics* (pp. 281-306). Academic Press.
- Sudha, M., & Sheena, K. (2017). Impact of influencers in consumer decision process: the fashion industry. *SCMS Journal of Indian Management*, 14(3), 14-30.
- Zhao, W. X., Liu, J., He, Y., Lin, C. Y., & Wen, J. R. (2016). A computational approach to measuring the correlation between expertise and social media influence for celebrities on microblogs. *World Wide Web*, 19(5), 865-886.

Appendix A

Table A1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.525 ^a	.276	.268	.74585

a. Predictors: (Constant), Authenticity, Expertise

Table A2

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	36.916	2	18.458	33.180	.000 ^b
Residual	96.796	174	.556		
Total	133.712	176			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction
b. Predictors: (Constant), Authenticity, Expertise

Table A3

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.870	.286		3.040	.003
	Expertise	.390	.091	.342	4.295	.000
	Authenticity	.244	.079	.245	3.075	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction